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The problem of improving the green economy using solar energy

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Abstract: This article discusses the future of green economy development using green energy in Central Asia. The main direction of research is analyzing the potential of renewable energy sources in the country and solving environmental and economic problems. This article is devoted to studying the problems of processing agricultural products produced in Central Asia using solar energy. The study results show that Central Asia has great potential for developing a green economy using green energy, which could lead to the creation of new jobs and an improvement in the environmental situation in the region.

Key words: green energy, green economy, renewable energy sources, solar energy, technical diagram, solar drying plant, energy security, food security.

1 Introduction

The implementation of the principles of a green economy in Central Asia through green energy is one of the priority areas. This article is devoted to studying the problems of processing agricultural products produced in Central Asia using solar energy. The goal of the research is to develop new technical schemes and installations for producing powders of agricultural products based on the use of solar energy as an alternative to the consumption of fossil fuels and electricity.

Central Asia has huge resources of one of the renewable energy sources - solar.

One of the ways to store agricultural products for a long time is to process it into a powder state. Processing agricultural products into a powder state simultaneously solves several problems: crop losses are reduced, storage problems are solved, transportation costs are reduced, there is no need to cool products during transportation, etc. One of the ways to reduce losses and long-term storage of fruits and vegetables is to dry them.

Drying is the most energy-intensive of all technological processes in the food industry. To evaporate 1 kg of water from food, 2480 kJ of energy is required. The share of energy consumption (coal, natural gas, etc.) in thermal dryers is up to 60% of the cost of finished powder products.

The economic development of the countries of Central Asia plays a key role in solving the social and economic problems of the region. Most of the population of Central Asia lives in rural areas, which is why the working population is involved in agriculture. About 40% of the population is employed in agriculture. Countries located in Central Asia have one of the highest levels of solar intensity in the world and are well positioned to

develop a green economy through green energy. The total area of the Central Asian states is 4,006,377 km², and the population is 81,065,256 million people [1,2].

Table 1.

State	Territory, km ²	Population (February 1, 2024)
Kazakhstan	2 724 902	20 053 665
Uzbekistan	448 924	37 029 360
Turkmenstan	491 200	7 057 841
Kyrgyzstan	199 951	7 037 590
Tajikistan	141 400	9 886 800
Total:	4 006 377	81 065 256

Therefore, combining these two resources and developing new technical schemes and installations for producing agricultural product powders using environmentally friendly and free solar energy is of great economic importance for Central Asia.

A new and promising direction in the green economy of Central Asia could be the production of food powders from plant materials using solar energy.

2 Materials and methods of research

Annual harvest losses of vegetables at the stage of procurement and storage in the countries of Central Asia are 5-25%, fruits - 15-18%. This not only leads to loss of actual yield, but also has an impact on the environment, labor, natural and energy resources in crop production.

On average, fruits and vegetables contain up to 90% water, 9.5% various organic compounds and 0.5% minerals. High water content means that fruits and vegetables are easily attacked by phytopathogens, and storing them after harvest is a challenge.

One of the ways to reduce losses and long-term storage of fruits and vegetables is to dry them. As a rule, agricultural products dried whole or in large parts contain 15-18% residual moisture. Strictly speaking, such moisture content also does not allow food to be stored for a long time. After some time, they begin to mold and are affected by microorganisms.

Solar energy has enormous potential as a renewable energy source due to the sparsely populated large areas and climatic conditions, especially in Central Asian countries where the sun shines between 2,200 and 3,000 hours per year. In the summer months (June–August), due to its geographical location, it receives direct solar radiation during most of the daylight hours, which is 83–96% of the maximum possible value. For comparison, the average number of sunshine hours in Vietnam is 2200, in China - 2500, in Germany, Great Britain, Norway and Japan - less than 1000 per year.

Under such actinometric conditions, it is practically possible to dry agricultural products using solar energy from April to the first half of November.

The cost of powder products obtained in a solar installation will be several times lower than the cost of products obtained by the traditional (thermal drying, use of fuel or electrical energy) method, since environmentally friendly, free solar energy is used for drying. [3,4].

The highest solar potential is estimated in Kazakhstan – 3,760,000 MW of solar photovoltaic energy. CADGAT (Central Asia Data Collection and Analysis Group) estimates the potential to be 6,684 TWh/year. With 2200–3000 hours of sunlight per year, solar radiation is 1200–1700 kW/m² or, according to another source, 1300–1800 kW/m².

In Kyrgyzstan, the solar photovoltaic energy potential is 267,000 MW. With solar radiation of 1000–1700 kW/m² (or 1500–1900 kW/m²), the solar energy potential is estimated at 490 GWh/year for thermal energy and 22.5 GWh/year for electrical energy. Another source estimates the potential at 700,000 GWh/year for electricity and about 2 billion Gcal/year for heat production.

In Tajikistan, the solar photovoltaic energy potential is estimated at 195,000 MW. With sunshine from 2100 to 3170 hours per year, 280–330 sunny days per year and solar radiation of 280–1120 MJ/m² or 0.9–8 kW/m², the solar potential is, according to various estimates, 25,000 GWh/ year, 410,000 GWh/year or 410 TWh/year.

Solar radiation is estimated at 1640–1690 kW/m². In Turkmenistan, where 80% of the territory is covered by the Karakum Desert and the annual duration of sunshine in some regions (for example, Kuli, Hasan and Ashgabat) ranges from 2700 to 3150 hours, the solar potential is significant.

In Uzbekistan, the solar photovoltaic energy potential is 593,000 MW. Solar potential is estimated from 525 and 760 GWh/year to a whopping 2,508,000 GWh/year, 2,000,000 GWh/year and 1,195 TWh/year. According to K. Jorde and A. Bigert, with 250 sunny days a year, the gross potential of solar energy is 593 million GWh, and the technically feasible potential is 2,000,000 GWh/year [5-12].

The potential of renewable energy sources, as shown in Table 2, is very significant in the Central Asian region. Small hydropower potential ranges from 275 to 30,000 MW, solar photovoltaic energy from 195,000 to 3,760,000 MW, wind energy from 1,500 to 354,000 MW, geothermal energy from 2 to 54,000 MW and bioenergy¹¹ from 200 to 800 MW. [13,14,15,16].

Table 2. Potential of renewable energy sources in Central Asia

country	Small hydropower	Solar photovoltaic energy		Wind energy		Geothermal energy	Bio-energy
	mW	mW	TWh/year	mW	TWh/year	TWh/year	mW
Kazakhstan	4800 (≤35 mW) 2707 (≤10 mW)	3760000	6684	354000	11 388	54 000	300
Kyrgyzstan	900 (≤30 mW) 275 (≤10 mW)	267 000	537	1500	256	171	200
Tajikistan	30 000 (≤30 mW)	195 000	410	2000	146	45	300
Turkmenistan	1300	655 000	1484	10 000	1992	No data	slightly
Uzbekistan	1180 (≤10 mW)	593 000	1195	1600	1685	2	800

In the technical scheme we are developing, the most important stage in obtaining SCP powders is drying the initial product. It is not only the most energy-intensive, but also the most important and influences the quality of the resulting powder: its composition, appearance, nutritional and taste qualities, shelf life, etc.

In the technical scheme for obtaining SCP powders that we have developed, drying is carried out using environmentally friendly and free solar energy. A mandatory and important step, which largely determines the effectiveness of such a scheme, is the conversion of the radiant energy of solar radiation into thermal energy and its supply to the dried agricultural product.

The technology being developed and solar installations intended for the implementation of such technology must take into account both the physical, mechanical, thermophysical properties of SCPs, different times of their maturation, as well as seasonal and daily variations in the density of solar radiation.

Such technological operations, which have become mandatory stages in the process of drying agricultural products when obtaining their powders, such as cleaning, washing, grinding into pieces, as well as finer grinding of the original product before drying to a liquid-viscous state, as well as grinding the dried agricultural products to a powdery state are also mandatory for technology we are developing [17,18,19, 20,21].

Our proposed technical scheme for producing SCP powders using solar energy should consist of the following main stages (technological operations) shown in Fig. 1.1.

According to the scheme, the initial product is first cleaned of foreign objects (leaves, small branches, weeds, etc.). Then it is washed (cleansed of dust and dirt). After this, large fruits (melon, watermelon, apple, pear, pumpkin, etc.) are divided into small pieces with characteristic dimensions of no more than 1.5 - 2 cm.

Small fruits and berries - apricots, strawberries, raspberries, grapes, cherries, etc., after washing, without preliminary chopping, are directly sent for grinding (apricots, cherries, sweet cherries, plums, etc. - after removing the seeds) . Products in a liquid-viscous form are laid out in pallets and placed in the drying chamber (DC) of a solar drying unit (SSU) and the drying process begins.

Fig.1.1. Block diagram of a technical solution for producing agricultural product powders using solar energy

A sign that the product has reached an extremely low residual moisture content is when the rate of change in the weight of the product reaches a horizontal or quasi-horizontal plateau. As our experiments have shown, the product reaches a residual moisture content not exceeding 3-8%, and for some products – 10%). After this, they are removed from the drying chamber.

During the experiments, heat was supplied to the dried products in three ways (Fig. 1.2):

- 1- radiation method (directly solar radiation) and convection;
- 2- infrared heating and convection;
- 3-pin heat supply and convection

Fig.1.2. Scheme of heat supply to dried products in a radiation-convective solar drying installation.

To implement the drying stage of liquid-viscous SCPs, we have developed two types of DCSs of the radiation-convective type: one with a single-pass movement of the coolant and the second with a two-pass movement of the coolant in the drying chamber (DC), the diagrams of which are shown in Fig. 1.3.

In the SSU with a single-pass movement of the coolant, the latter passes once simultaneously from the upper and lower sides of the pallets with SCP. Since hot air is displaced to the upper part of the combustor, it can be assumed that the product receives thermal energy from the coolant from the upper (open) surface in a convective manner.

In a DCS with a two-pass coolant movement, the latter first passes from the bottom side of the pallets, and then, turning at the end of the CS, passes over the products being dried. In this case, the coolant first gives off heat by convection to this part of the pallets (which is then transferred to the lower layers of products adjacent to the pallets), and then, again by convection, gives off the remaining part of the thermal energy to the products from their upper surface. This should help more intense heating of the lower part of the products adjacent to the tray and, accordingly, intensify the drying process.

The novelty of the technical solution of the developed SSUs is that they make it possible to dry liquid-viscous agricultural products to low (3-8%) residual moisture even at low values of solar radiation due to the use of heating elements in direct contact with the products, which are heated from absorbed solar radiation by the upper, blackened sides.

The proposed SSU works as follows: solar radiation (direct + diffuse), penetrating through the upper transparent fence of the SCS, heats the air inside it. This air, passing through the transition (docking) block 5, enters the compressor station. At the same time, it passes simultaneously above and below the pallets 6 with products and gives them its thermal energy.

It should be noted that the movement of air through the SVK and KS occurs under natural pressure ΔP , which arises due to the difference in the densities of atmospheric (relatively cold) air and heated air in the SVK and KS [22]:

$$\Delta P = g h (\rho_x - \rho_g)$$

where g is the acceleration of free fall, h is the vertical distance from the entrance slit of the SVK to the top of the exhaust pipe of the CS, ρ_x is the density of atmospheric air, ρ_g is the density of the steam-air mixture at the outlet of the exhaust pipe.

In the experiments, we measured the following parameters of the products, the drying process and the drying units themselves:

1. Density of integral solar radiation. The measurements were made with an M-80M pyranometer with a measurement range of $0 \div 1200 \text{ W/m}^2$.

2. Temperature of the ambient air, as well as the air heated in the SSU and the steam-air mixture at the exit from the SSU drying chamber. The ambient air temperature was measured using a laboratory mercury thermometer of accuracy class 1.0, with a ...where g is the acceleration of free fall, h is the vertical distance from the entrance slit of the SVK to the top of the exhaust pipe of the CS, ρ_x is the density of atmospheric air, ρ_g is the density of the steam-air mixture at the outlet of the exhaust pipe.

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2. Temperature of the ambient air, as well as the air heated in the SSU and the steam-air mixture at the exit from the SSU drying chamber. The ambient air temperature was measured using a laboratory mercury thermometer of accuracy class 1.0, with a measurement range of $0 \div 100^\circ\text{C}$ in the shade, near the SSU.

3. The air temperature inside the SSU, on the surface layer and in the middle of the dried liquid-viscous and whole (or divided into large pieces) product was measured using calibrated copper-constantan thermocouples, the readings of which were recorded by a GSA-1 galvanometer.

4. The temperature on the surface of products dried in the open air and the temperature of the glass coating of the SSU drying chamber were measured using a non-contact infrared thermometer INF-200 with a measurement error of $\pm 2\%$. The measurement range is from -20°C to $+420^\circ\text{C}$.

Fig.1.3. Schemes of developed solar drying installations for drying liquid-viscous agricultural products: a – SSU with single-pass coolant movement, b – SSU with two-pass coolant movement.

1 – solar air heating collector, 2 – drying chamber, 3 – glass coating, 4 – radiation-absorbing metal blackened plates of the SVC, 5 – adapter block, 6 – pallets with dried products, 7 – exhaust pipe, 8 – load-bearing metal frame.

Initial, current and final weights of dried products. The weights of the dried products were measured using electronic scales brand CAS SWH - 03 with a maximum weighing weight of 3 kg and measurement accuracy of ± 1 gram.

We have studied the following types of products that are of greatest practical interest in using them in powder form:

1. Fruits: apple, pear, cherry, sweet cherry, white grapes, black grapes, plum, pear, quince;
2. Melon berries: strawberries, raspberries, melon and watermelon;
3. Vegetables: tomatoes, yellow carrots, red carrots, cabbage, potatoes, green and red bell peppers, pumpkin, radish (turup), red beets, garlic and onions.

In the experiments, drying in the SSU and in the open air (air-solar drying) began at 9 a.m. Until this time, the products were crushed, laid out on pallets, measured (weighed) their initial weight, prepared the SSU and a set of measuring instruments - a pyranometer, installed thermometers, introduced and fixed thermocouples into the dried products.

The results of drying in a combustor with one-pass and two-pass coolant movement are presented.

Fig.1.4. Results of drying apricots in July 1 – built-in solar radiation lamp, t – ambient temperature, 1, 2 – air – solar drying, 3, 4 – SSU drying; 1 and 3 – with IKNE, 2 and 4 – radiation-convective drying, 5 – radiation-convective drying of apricot halves in SSU. and 35-36oC respectively).

Fig.1.5. The results of drying liquid-viscous agricultural products in October in the SSU by the radiation-convective method: E - solar radiation density, t – ambient air temperature, 1 – apple, 2 - quince, 3 – tomatoes.

3 Conclusion

Thus, in general, new technologies for using solar energy for drying liquid-viscous agricultural products in the production of powders provide economic benefits. In addition, the use of environmentally friendly solar energy will significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions, primarily CO₂, and improve the environmental situation in the country.

When put into practice on an industrial scale, the developed technical scheme for obtaining powders of agricultural products using solar energy will allow saving energy resources, significantly reduce crop losses during storage, to a certain extent solve the problem of ensuring food security in the region, the problem of employment, will increase the export potential of Central Asia, improve the environmental situation in the country, as well as transport costs their transportation is almost 10 times.

The implementation of these recommendations contributes to the solution of four priority tasks for Central Asia:

- food security;
- rational use of natural resources (agricultural products);
- saving fuel and energy resources;
- environmental protection.

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